

People management in mergers and acquisitions in Sri Lanka: Employee perceptions

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Abstract

Though there is an increasing interest in and a growing amount of literature available on people management aspects of M&As, few studies have empirically examined employee experiences. Further, no such studies have been conducted in the Asian developing country context. From a practical standpoint results will provide practitioners with information that would be valuable for better understanding of employee experiences of M&As to better understand and address people management issues in M&As. The aim of the article is to present, compare and discuss empirical evidence on employees' interpretations of their experiences of people management in two different types of bank mergers- extension merger and collaborative merger in Sri Lanka. For the study two banks were selected which had undergone an extension merger and a collaborative merger. 109 employees from the two banks responded to the survey questionnaire. The findings led to reveal that the employee perceptions are affected by the type of the merger and employees are less satisfied in the collaborative merger than in the extension merger. Further, findings led to reveal that age, gender and marital status do influence the perceptions of the respondents and among those age is the most influencing variable. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Key words- mergers, acquisitions, people management, Sri Lanka

Introduction

Mergers and acquisitions (M&As) are becoming an increasingly popular strategic option for organizations (Chew and Sharma, 2005; Marks and Mirvis, 2001; McEntire and Bentley, 1996). From the 1980s countries have witnessed an increase in M&As between firms of different sizes and different industry types (Tetenbaum, 1999) and this trend does not seem to show signs of diminishing in the near future. Advantages that could be achieved through M&As are well documented (Birkinshaw et al, 2000; Marks and Mirvis, 1996; Napier, 1989).

Though due diligence includes numerous financial elements, at the core of reasons for success/failure of M&As are personnel and behavioural issues, such as blending cultures and several sets of policies, practices and procedures of the two organizations; designing the new organization and its jobs, and loss of key personnel, all of which indicate the importance of the human factor (Appelbaum et al., 2000a, 2000b; Cartwright and Cooper, 1995; Risberg, 1997; Rhoades, 1998; Schuler and Jackson, 2001). However, human aspects tend to take second place to commercial and financial considerations in M&A's and are often neglected (Huang and Kleiner, 2004).

Understanding employees' experiences of M&As is important for several reasons. First, although there is lot of literature available on people management aspects of M&As, much of the information is anecdotal or offers prescriptive advices or very general case studies (Mirvis, 1985; Schweiger and Weber, 1989). As Napier (1989) noted there is no dearth of literature on the topic but there is a dearth of research. Published material provides little significant evidence supporting their findings and recommendations. Second, there is an increasing evidence for the need of an

ongoing analysis of employee perceptions towards employee relations, remuneration, performance evaluation, training, and other related aspects before and after a merger/acquisition has been consummated (Dolan and Weil, 1998). Third, individual differences in terms of demographic characteristics could influence the interpretations of their experiences. However, M&A research addressing differences in employee perceptions by gender, age, or marital status are not available. Therefore, investigations are required to identify needs and concerns of the individuals to gain support to M&As (Schraeder and Self, 2003). This constitutes an important gap in the M&A literature. The analysis in this article addresses this, presenting empirical evidence of employees' experiences of people management in two different bank mergers in Sri Lanka.

For the study two banks were selected which had undergone two types of merger: an extension merger and a collaborative merger. Literature suggests that employee perceptions could be affected by the type of the merger (Napier, 1989). Therefore, specific aims of the article are to present, compare and discuss the results of employees' interpretations of their experiences of people management in M&As of the two banks in terms of: 1) the level of satisfaction employees have with the information received; 2) communication consequences; 3) employee expectations following the merger; 4) the actual situation employees experience following the merger; 5) consequences following the merger; 6) the level of satisfaction employees have with the involvement of human resource department in the merger. As the two banks investigated belong to two different types of mergers, it is expected that there would be significant differences in employee perceptions by bank. Further, it is expected that there would be significant differences in employees' interpretations of their experiences in terms of age, gender or marital status of the individuals. Therefore, the article addresses the findings of the study at three levels, namely, the results of the data analysis of responses given by the total sample of respondents, the comparison

of results by the type of the merger, and the comparison of results by demographic variables namely age, gender and marital status. However, it should be noted that the study conducted was basic in nature to identify specific research areas to be further investigated using interviews and analysis of archival material. In order to provide the context for the article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Context of the Study

Sri Lanka had been under Western rule (Portuguese, Dutch and British) for several centuries and became independent in 1948. At the time of regaining independence, Sri Lanka was mainly an agricultural economy. The production of and trade in three plantation crops – tea, rubber and coconut– contributed to a major share of the national income. There was little interaction between the plantation sector and the domestic non-plantation agricultural sector. The plantation sector performance dominated the activities of the other sectors of the economy such as trade, banking, insurance, transport and manufacturing. By the time of regaining independence, the economy was open to free trade and exports and imports accounted for about 70 per cent of gross domestic product (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). However, from the mid 1960s the governments of Sri Lanka had gradually introduced an array of controls to promote local industrial and agricultural activities. In 1977, far-reaching policy reforms were introduced to free the economy from the array of controls (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Since 1977, the Sri Lankan governments have adopted an economic strategy designed to industrialize through foreign direct investment. On the other hand, in response to several factors, such as increasing global competition, lower labour costs

in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan governments, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing since 1977.

The financial sector of the country was dominated by the foreign owned (foreign-privately owned and foreign-government owned) commercial banks at the time of regaining independence. They engaged almost exclusively in the financing of the plantation sector and import and export trade. Since 1950s, a wide array of financial institutions has been established (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Among these, the most important ones are Central Bank of Sri Lanka, licensed commercial banks (LCBs), licensed specialised banks (LSBs), registered finance companies (RFCs), specialised leasing companies (SLCs), pension and provident funds, insurance companies, rural banks, merchant banks, unit trusts and thrift and credit co-operative societies. The major growth in financial services occurred after the liberalization of the economy in 1977. This is clearly reflected in the growth of assets of financial institutions and the contribution of the financial sector to GDP.

Sri Lanka is one of the countries having a well-developed human resource base in Asia. The total working age population of the country was 16.9 million in 2005, of which 48.2 per cent were economically active: 67 per cent males and 33 per cent females (Dept. of Census and Statistics, 2005). Sri Lanka is trying to promote gender equality in terms of increasing women's participation in the workforce and in terms of the range of jobs open to them. The labour force participation rate for males is 94 per cent for those who are in the age range of 25 - 29 years. The highest participation rate for females is reported as 45 per cent in the age range of 30 - 39 years. However, there is no significant change in labour force participation rate in year 2005, compared to previous years. Of the total employees, 69 per cent were engaged in the non-agricultural work (25% in industries and 44% in services). Though no specific segregation of data on financial sector is

available, of the total male employees 46 per cent and of the total female employees 38 per cent were engaged in services. Of the employed females in the total workforce, 22 per cent has an educational qualification of General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) or above, compared to a proportion of 13 percent employed males having the same level of education (Dept. of Census and Statistics, 2005). Therefore, one of the significant observations in Sri Lanka is the increasing number of educated women entering into the economically active population and this trend is projected to continue.

Theoretical background

Mergers and acquisitions

A merger is the integration of two previously discrete entities. It occurs when two firms integrate to form a new organization with shared resources and corporate objectives (Horwitz et al, 2002).

An acquisition occurs when an organization acquires sufficient shares to gain control or ownership of another organization (Horwitz et al, 2002). For the purpose of this study the terms mergers and acquisitions (M&As) are used interchangeably because the result is the same – one organization takes control of another (Waight, 2004).

There is a growing amount of publications exists on different aspects of M&As (Appelbaum and Gandell, 2003; Conyon et al, 2002; Griffith, 2000; Gugler and Yurtoglu, 2003). However, most research might be framed in terms of the discipline it originates from such as economics, finance, organizational behaviour and strategic management (Papadakis, 2005). Behavioural research stream mainly deals with corporate culture (Bijlsma-Frankema, 2001; Burns and Rosen, 1997; Riad, 2007; Stahl and Voigt, 2004), structure (Mirvis, 1985), and human resource policies (Kerr,

1995). Mergers and acquisitions cannot realize their full potential without positive employee input. Yet, M&As significantly affect the working lives of employees. However, not enough attention is given to employees' experiences of people management aspects in M&As in behavioural research stream.

Employee experiences of M&As

The available literature on employees' experiences suggests that the first consideration of employees in M&As is how it will impact on them personally as M&A is a beginning of a period of uncertainty and unpredictability (Csoka, 1997; Shirley 1973). There are many emotions encountered in the workplace due to the expectations, questions, and reservations among the employees at all levels of both organizations. It is not uncommon for management to use M&As as an opportunity to reduce staff and claw back employment conditions (Bryson, 2003; Craven, 2004; Schweiger and Weber, 1989). Hence, employees often articulate many fears about personal impacts that they are confronted with following an M&A, of which the most obvious is losing one's job. Others include changes in pay and benefits, changes in the job, roles and assignments, changes in performance evaluation systems, transfers to new jobs/geographical locations, changes in career paths, changes in bosses and co-workers, changes in organizational power, status and prestige, changes in corporate culture and loss of identity with the organization, etc (Huang and Kleiner, 2004; Ivancevich, et al, 1987). A high level of uncertainty could result in higher absenteeism, stress, low job satisfaction, a general negative behaviour, resistance to change, lower productivity and commitment to the organization (Papadakis, 2005; Nikandrou et al., 2000; Schweiger and Weber, 1989).

In the above context, M&A literature identifies that maintaining the stability of the workforce throughout a merger as a key priority. The literature reveals that the same merger rumours, facts and activities would be perceived as a threat by one person and an opportunity by another. As work is an integral part of most people's lives and helps them attain the things that they value, M&As are powerful events that have the potential to change these relationships. However, not all M&As threaten the outcomes and values that the work provides. The fears could be offset by several hopes, which include advancement opportunities, meeting new people and forming new working relationships, learning new skills, and setting new goals as well as creating an organization that is better than the two originally separate organizations (Marks and Mirvis, 1992). Though these might enhance value attainment, until the initial shock is over and the dust begins to settle, seeing personal benefits from M&As is difficult (Ivancevich, et al, 1987).

Since the perceived events and consequences were deemed to be an important part of employees' lives, (Marks, 2006), in the absence of actual information concerning the M&A, an individual's appraisal will be determined primarily by his/her speculations about events that might occur and rumours associated with them. In this context, frequent and honest communication to employees has a stabilizing effect (Marks and Mirvis, 1997; Schweiger and DeNisi 1991). Further, a number of programmes, such as stress management training, career counselling, merger sensitisation workshops, small group meetings, etc. have been suggested to help facilitate the coping process (Eisenberger et al. 1990; Elliot and Maples, 1991). Further, re-training programmes help employees develop new job skills, and training in conflict resolution and team building help employees deal with new work situations (Covin et al., 1996; Kusstatscher, 2006; Pollitt, 2004; Schweiger and Weber, 1989; Yeung et al. 1991).

Types of M&As and people management aspects

Napier (1989) suggests that motives and characteristics of the merging firms may suggest a type of merger to pursue- whether extension, collaborative or redesign. Extension mergers typically develop out of non-value maximizing motives and would be expected to be conglomerate mergers (Napier, 1989; Pikula, 1999). This involves the acquisition of an unrelated business, which provides profitable diversification. Collaborative mergers occur when two firms whose product or service is closely related or of the same type join to generate gains through a blending of operations, assets or cultures, or through an exchange of technology or other expertise (Napier, 1989). Redesign merger is likely to be common in related acquisitions- concentric mergers. The motive for redesign mergers may be the desire of one firm to gain control of the management or Board of another firm (Napier, 1989).

The literature suggests that the type of the merger could influence human resource (HR) practices (Napier, 1989; Pikula, 1999). In an extension merger since the two firms are unrelated in product or service, internal changes to the acquired firm, which will remain relatively autonomous, are likely to be minimal, and there will be few cultural consequences (Pikula, 1999). Thus, the impact on HR and other practices in an extension merger is likely to be low (Napier, 1989). On the other hand, from a HR perspective, collaborative mergers are the most difficult mergers to be implemented, since the acquiring firm already has expertise in the business operations and will act to consolidate the two firms to avoid redundancy and become more cost-effective. Downsizing and voluntary quits usually recede or immediately follow the merger (Pikula, 1999).

Research problem area

Napier (1989) suggests that the type of the merger that the firms are going to pursue may help plan for and implement the required changes in HR practices. However, M&A literature does not provide data of empirical research on employee experiences of M&As. Especially, though literature suggests that people management matters have to be handled differently in extension and collaborative mergers, no empirical studies available. Hence, there is a need for better understanding of employee experiences of M&As to better understand and address people management issues in M&As. If people management aspects are not designed according to the type of the M&A, it could be expected that there would be differences in employees' interpretations in terms of: 1) the level of satisfaction employees have with the information received; 2) communication consequences; 3) employee expectations following the merger; 4) the actual situation employees experience following the merger; 5) consequences following the merger; 6) the level of satisfaction employees have with the involvement of HR department in the merger. Therefore, this research assumes that there would be differences in employees' interpretations of their experiences of people management aspects of extension mergers and collaborative mergers. Further, when drawing upon evidence from organizational behavior and psychology related research, individual differences in terms of demographic characteristics could influence the interpretations of their experiences. In this regard, the vast majority of M&A studies have been undertaken primarily in the West, US in particular. The extent to which employee experiences of these countries could be generalized to Asian context has not been widely tested. It could be assumed that what is wanted by individuals from one country in terms of jobs could be different from what is wanted by individuals from another country. Therefore, there could be differences in employees' interpretations of their experiences of people management aspects of

M&As in terms of cultural demographic characteristics such as age, gender and marital status.

Therefore, the article intends to address the findings of the study at three levels, namely, the results of the data analysis of responses given by the total sample of respondents, the comparison of results by the type of the merger, and the comparison of results by demographic variables- age, gender and marital status.

Empirical research context

To achieve the objectives of the study, two bank mergers were investigated. The resulting two banks following the mergers are identified as BankAB (the merger of BankA and BankB) and BankCD (the merger of BankC and BankD). BankAB could be identified as a result of an extension merger while BankCD could be identified as a result of a collaborative merger. Brief descriptions of the banks are as follows.

BankAB

From its formation in 1979, as a fully government owned entity, the BankA played a catalytic role as a leading development bank lending for large scale projects in every economic sectors through a network of branches across the country. After its successful transition to a privatised entity in 1993, the BankA expanded its range of financial products and services as a successful leading domestic development bank in Sri Lanka. There were approximately 530 employees in BankA. As most of the commercial banks of the country have entered into the lending industry with new marketing strategies it has been difficult for BankA to dominant in the market with a single business line. This led BankA to acquire or merge with a commercial bank operating in Sri Lanka.

BankB, which was established in Sri Lanka in 1979, was a foreign private owned bank. There were about 130 employees in BankB. By the early 2000, BankB planned to closedown its Sri Lankan operations as a part of restructuring of its global operations as well as relatively poor prospects in Sri Lanka. BankA and two other local commercial banks were interested in acquiring BankB. Even though BankA's bid was the lowest, it was identified as the successor by Central Bank of Sri Lanka above the other two commercial banks. Thus, BankA acquired BankB and got merged in August 2003. The merged bank is referred as BankAB in this article.

After the merger, BankAB remains as a local owned domestic bank. There are about 710 employees in BankAB. It has introduced debit cards, phone banking and Internet banking after the merger. The bank is also planning to enter into the credit card business. As BankA and BankB were from two different specialized areas of business, Bank AB had not laid off any employee due to the acquisition and merger.

BankCD

BankC, which was established in Sri Lanka in 1892, was a foreign private owned bank in the commercial banking operations specialized in consumer credit through credit cards. It had 8 branches in Sri Lanka with about 180 employees. Though BankC had gone series of evolution during its existence in Sri Lanka, by the late 1990s Sri Lankan operations were running at a loss. According to the details given in the BankC's web site, it is listed on both the London Stock Exchange and Stock Exchange of Hong Kong and is in the top FTSE-100 companies.

BankD, which was established in Sri Lanka in 1881, was also a foreign private owned bank in the commercial banking operations. It had 7 branches in Sri Lanka with approximately 325 employees. In the year 2000, BankC acquired Middle East and South Asia Operations of BankD. Thus, the Sri Lankan wings had to merge their operations under the supervision of the international head office. The merged bank is referred as BankCD in this article.

After the merger too BankCD remains as a foreign private owned commercial bank operating in Sri Lanka. Integration process of BankC and BankD involved streamlining of the operational aspects of the two banks and introduction of new technology. However, the revenue contribution from the Sri Lankan operations is low- around 4 percent within the Middle East and South Asia- where as in terms of staff numbers it accounts for around 12 percent- the highest in the region. The original staff strength when alliance become formal was over 500 in the two banks (BankC and BankD) and currently stands around 380 in the BankCD. It was in 2001 that the first phase of the voluntary retirement scheme was introduced and was accepted by around 60 staff members. The second phase of the voluntary retirement scheme was introduced in the year 2002 and it was accepted by around 100 employees. Both BankC and BankD have prior experiences of M&As over the years of their global existence.

Data collection instrument and methods of data analysis

For the study, a self-administered questionnaire was designed as the research instrument. Though the majority of M&A literature is anecdotal or offers prescriptive advices or very general case studies, it was decided to get insight from those in constructing the questionnaire. Considering the literacy of the target population and amenability of the research questions, the questionnaire was

constructed in the English language. Most of the questions took the form of closed-ended with responses on a Likert scale, as this approach has proven to be more efficient and ultimately more reliable. To address the research objectives of the study, the areas covered in the survey questionnaire were as follows:

- The methods used to communicate about the merger- invited the respondent to indicate methods used to communicate by simply ticking the communication methods used. An item labelled “other” was also added to the list;
- The level of satisfaction with the information received- listed a range of items. A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘very dissatisfied’ to (5) ‘very satisfied’ is used;
- Communication consequences- A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’ is used;
- Expectations following the merger- A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’ is used;
- The actual situation following the merger- A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘strongly disagree’ to (5) ‘strongly agree’ is used;
- Consequences following the merger- A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’ is used;
- The level of satisfaction with the involvement of HR department in the merger- A five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’ is used.

The questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of 20 employees from both BankAB and BankCD to get their comments on the readability, accuracy and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire. After several revisions, the questionnaire was distributed in 2006 to the employees employed in BankAB who were attached either to BankA or BankB prior to the merger and to the

employees employed in BankCD who were attached either to BankC or BankD prior to the merger. 109 respondents (57-BankAB, 52-BankCD) voluntarily responded within 4 weeks of questionnaire distribution. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the sample. The z statistic and associated significance value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test indicated that the shape of the two distributions of employees from BankAB and BankCD is not significantly different for gender (K-S $z=.26$, $p>.05$), marital status (K-S $z=.46$, $p>.05$), age (K-S $z=.05$, $p>.05$), or profession (K-S $z=.26$, $p>.05$).

Take in Table 1

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS. Inter-item correlation test was conducted separately for each of the set of items investigated. Test results for each category received standardized item alpha values higher than .7, i.e., for the items on the level of information satisfaction .71, communication consequences .79, expectations following the merger .77, etc. As the research aimed to compare and to identify significant differences in employee experiences by the type of the merger and demographic characteristics (age, gender or marital status), independent sample t-test was conducted as the main method of data analysis.

Results

The level of satisfaction employees have with information received

With regard to the methods used to communicate information regarding the merger, of the 109 total respondents, 100 received information during staff meetings (BankAB 51, and BankCD 49);

77 received information through e-mail/intranet (BankAB 54, and BankCD 23) and 28 from BankAB also received information from public news papers. Thus, the results suggest that the two banks used more than one medium. However, although data source methods such as official letters and newsletters were mentioned in the questionnaire as options, none of the respondents indicated that banks had used these. Since not all employees necessarily receive the same information, respondents were asked to indicate their level of satisfaction with the information received. The results are shown in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

Table 3 shows the differences in the level of satisfaction with the information received by age, gender and marital status.

Take in Table 3

Communication consequences

Table 4 shows the level of communication consequences. All the items considered have significant differences by the bank, where employees from BankCD suffered more.

Take in Table 4

Table 5 shows the differences in terms of age, gender and marital status. None of the items considered had significant differences by gender or by marital status.

Take in Table 5

Employee expectations following the merger

Table 6 shows employees' expectations following the merger.

Take in Table 6

The actual situation employees experience following the merger

Table 7 shows employee perceptions for the actual situation following the merger.

Take in Table 7

Consequences following the merger

Consequences following the merger are shown in Table 8. Overall, results do not reveal high level of job satisfaction following the merger.

Take in Table 8

The differences in employee perceptions by age, gender and marital status are shown in table 9.

Take in Table 9

The level of satisfaction employees have with the involvement of HR department in the merger

Table 10 shows employees' level of satisfaction with the involvement of HR function in the merger.

Take in Table 10

Differences in perceptions by age, gender and marital status are shown in table 11.

Take in Table 11

Discussion, concluding remarks and managerial implications

The main objective of this investigation was to evaluate employees' experiences of people management aspects in M&As and to report empirical evidence from Sri Lanka. The article addressed the findings of the study at three levels, namely, the results of the data analysis of responses given by the total sample of respondents, the comparison of results by the type of the merger, and the comparison of results by demographic variables- age, gender and marital status.

First, the findings of the data analysis of 109 responses suggested that the number of media used in the communication of the M&A is limited though communication and information flow can take a variety of forms. However, according to the findings, the majority of the employees received information during staff meetings, where employees can voice their opinions, concerns and desires and responding to their questions with information that is known at the time. In this regard, Lengle and Daft (1988) and Richardson and Denton (1996) argue that all forms of communication do not have the same effect and Lengle and Daft (1988) suggest that though routine messages be best sent through lean forms of media such as memos and e-mails when the message becomes increasingly non-routine it is important to communicate through richer forms of media, such as face-to-face meetings. The findings further suggested that considerable number of respondents received information from public news papers. In this regard, literature provides evidence to the role that media plays in shaping the social context for M&As (Schneider and Dunbar, 1992). For instance, Schraeder and Self (2003) suggest that during M&As media could fuel anxieties or constrain anxieties depending on the journalistic perspective presented. Napier et al (1989) suggests that whether management communicates or not, employees will seek answers to their questions. Findings of the study also revealed the high level of reliance on gossips regarding the merger, a high level of rumours being spread regarding the mergers and high level of uncertainty about the future. Inaccurate rumours would intensify employees' anxieties. Schweiger and DeNisi (1991) suggest that it is the uncertainty that creates stress for the members rather than the actual changes associated with the merger. Therefore, the lack of satisfaction with the information received could result in employees feeling apprehensive and even hostile toward the merger, making any subsequent communication difficult. In this regard, numerous recommendations concerning communication philosophy, communication media, and types of information to communicate abound in the literature (Marks and Mirvis, 2001; Schweiger and Weber, 1989).

Though M&A literature identifies losing one's job as the most articulated fear that employees are confronted with following a merger (Bryson, 2003; Marks and Mirvis, 1992), the findings of this study suggest that the employees mostly expected changes in salary and other financial benefits and changes in performance evaluation system. It is logical for employees to expect changes in these HR policy areas as those affect all types of employees, are more technical in nature and likely to lead to cross-firm comparisons among employees. Therefore, this emphasizes the need for consistency of HR policies.

Findings of the actual situation faced by the employees following the merger revealed that some had to compete for the same job with colleagues due to lay offs. This suggests that employees felt threatened by the seemingly high level of talent in the merged organization. Findings of the actual situation further revealed that career prospects and prospects for training and development have not highly improved in the merged organizations though Millward and Kyriakidou (2004) identified that individual's aspirations could be balanced with business needs and subjective permanence can be assured by actively managing individual careers and opportunities for development.

There are two general types of outcomes of M&As commonly mentioned in the literature- objective performance measures and employee reaction measures (Napier, 1989). In the study, the employee reactions were investigated. The findings suggested that employee's attitudes in the areas of job satisfaction and commitment are not at high levels. However, the findings also revealed that improvements in individual identity as an employee following the merger is moderate. M&A literature suggests that as long as employees view merger as an opportunity to

preserve or enhance one's self-esteem, it could help to increase employees' overall adjustment (Ivancevich et al, 1987). Though findings suggest that employees do not feel highly as if given false promises, merger encouraged them to look for employment opportunities elsewhere. Thus, results suggest that merger might be traumatic for some, who are long-term employees with dissolved banks, leading them to seek other opportunities. Thus, the findings imply the importance of realistic communication through the form of a realistic merger preview that appraise or re-appraise the situation faced by the employees to minimize the problems of employee adjustment. However, the findings also suggested that employees are less satisfied with HR departments' involvement in mergers. Though M&A literature identifies the importance of counselling on an individual basis to help employees overcome fear and help alleviate negative reactions (Pikula, 1999), the findings revealed that employees are less satisfied with its provision.

Since BankA and BankB are from two different areas of specialization, in the merger of BankAB, BankA acquired BankB for growth related reasons- as a way to diversity. On the other hand, the merger of BankCD could be identified as a merger of equals, where both BankC and BankD were foreign owned banks operating in commercial banking activities in Sri Lanka. Though the review of M&A literature revealed that mergers of related firms are more likely to realize synergies than mergers of unrelated firms (Appelbaum, 2000a, 2000b), in this study scope was to explore employee perceptions. Employee perceptions for the extension merger of BankAB are more positive than employee perceptions for the merger of BankCD, which is a collaborative merger. Thus, employees from BankCD would find that they are working with their former competitors. They have highly expected job loss, felt more uncertain about their future, and have to work much harder to keep their existing position in the merged bank, which led them to search employment opportunities in other organizations following the merger. It could be noted that dissatisfied

employees from BankCD could provoke discontent among others. Employee perceptions imply that in the merger of BankC and BankD, the changes expected in the people management aspects are much higher and they are less satisfied than in the merger of BankA and BankB. Thus, the findings imply that the employee perceptions could be affected by the type of the merger.

Further findings revealed that there are some differences in employee perceptions by age, gender and marital status. Respondents belong to the young age group were less satisfied with the information received on changes in banks identity, changes in administration system, about job security, and changes in reporting relations while respondents belong to older age group were less satisfied with the information received on changes in salary and other financial benefits. Further respondents belong to older age group revealed that they felt uncertain about their future, they have to concentrate planning their future career, and felt as if they were given false promises than respondents belong to the young age group. With regard to the satisfaction with the involvement of the HR function in the merger, respondents belong to the older age group were less satisfied. In terms of gender, females were less satisfied with the information received on changes in reporting relations, and find that they have to concentrate planning their future career than males. In terms of marital status, unmarried respondents were less satisfied with the HR involvement in organizing staff events involving employees from both banks that intend to merge. Therefore, findings of the t-test imply that demographic variables do influence the perceptions of the respondents and among those age is the most influencing variable.

Overall, this article contributes to an important dimension of people management aspects in M&As. As there could be different HR policies and practices exist in the banks that intended to merge, it is evident that employees are concerned of the possible changes and the way in which

those were handled and how those affects the individual's employment relationship. Thus, from the employees' perspective, M&A brings uncertainty. It also implied that the merger encouraged some to look for employment elsewhere. Although attractive benefits could be instituted to retain individuals, these palliatives might not be sufficient to retain employees as findings had not revealed high level of satisfaction with the situation following the merger. However, findings of this study are not sufficient to comment conclusively on the extent to which employees are made to feel part of the day-to-day organization and accepted as members of the new team. Findings also implied the importance of the effort and dedication from HR departments in the merger. On one hand, the involvement of the HR function is a matter of a humanitarian concern for absorbing grief among employees. In the both situations investigated in the study, as argued by Hunsaker and Coombs (1988) related to merger-emotions syndrome, the time period for the feelings of denial, fear, anger and sadness had elapsed. Therefore, what is the most important is preparing employees to become hopeful about the new situation, preparing them to perceive the new situation as a challenge in which they can prove their abilities and worth to their organization, and helping them to discover new opportunities that they had not envisioned before (merger-emotions syndrome, Hunsaker and Coombs 1988, p58). On the other hand, it is also implied that HR professionals have to be cognizant of the entire process, including the desired outcomes, and should possess skills and experience to handle the sensitive people management areas of M&As effectively.

Limitations and directions for future research

The study has some limitations. The study was confined to investigate employees' interpretations of their experiences of people management in two different types of bank mergers- extension merger and collaborative merger. Though there are two general types of outcomes of M&As

commonly mentioned in the literature- objective performance measures and employee perception measures- the current study is based on employee perceptions utilizing self-report measures. When considering the sample selected for the study, all the respondents could be labelled as those who “survived” the merger. This happens due to difficulties in contacting the employees those who left due to the merger. Further, this study was conducted as a preliminary investigation to identify specific research areas to be investigated using interviews and analysis of archival material. Therefore there is a need to triangulate the findings of this study with data from other sources.

As previously noted, very little work has been directed toward the identification of employee experiences of M&As. There are several possible areas where this study could be expanded. One possible area for the investigation is the influence of the type of the merger on the extent to which people management practices of the two organizations are integrated following the merger. There is a need for an ongoing analysis of employee perceptions towards human resource management practices relating to M&As such as performance evaluation, career development, salary and other benefits before, during and the first few years after a merger has been consummated. Thus, detailed investigations could be conducted on each of the people management aspects to compare how those have been handled in the two types of mergers. Thus, the current study could be extended to various directions as the questionnaire survey provided access to the breadth of experience while qualitative research methods such as interviews and archival information may provide further insight and substance to survey data.

References

Appelbaum, S., Gandell, J., Yortis, H., Proper, S., Jobin, F. (2000a), “Anatomy of a merger: behavior of organizational factors and processes throughout the pre during post-stages (part 1)”, *Management Decision*, 38 (9): 649-61.

Appelbaum, S., Gandell, J., Yortis, H., Proper, S., and Jobin, F. (2000b), “Anatomy of a merger: behavior of organizational factors and processes throughout the pre during post-stages (part 2)”, *Management Decision*, 38 (10): 674-84.

Appelbaum, S.H., Gandell, J. (2003), “A cross method analysis of the impact of culture and communications upon a health care merger Prescriptions for human resources management”, *Journal of Management Development*, 22 (5): 370-409.

Bijlsma-Frankema, K. (2001), “On managing cultural integration and cultural change processes in mergers and acquisitions”, *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 192-207.

Birkinshaw, J., Bresman, H., Hakanson, L. (2000), “Managing the post-acquisition integration process”, *Journal of Management Studies*, 37 (3): 395-425.

Bryson, J. (2003), “Managing HRM risk in a merger”, *Employee Relations*, 25 (1): 14-30.

Burns, M., Rosen, A. (1997), “HR aspects of a take-over: Ferraris and limousines – tales from the cultural body shop”, *Career Development International*, 2(5): 219-24.

Cartwright, S., Cooper, G. (1995), ““Organizational marriage: ‘hard’ versus ‘soft’ issues?””, *Personnel Review*, 24(3): 32-42.

Central Bank of Sri Lanka (1998) *Economic Progress of Independent Sri Lanka: 1948–1998*. Colombo: Central Bank of Sri Lanka.

Chew, I.K.H., Sharma, B. (2005), “The effects of culture and HRM practices on firm performance: Empirical evidence from Singapore”, *International Journal of Manpower*, 26(6): 560-581

Conyon, M.J., Girma, S., Thompson, S., Wright, P.W. (2002), “The impact of mergers and acquisitions on company employment in the United Kingdom”, *European Economic Review*, 46: 31-49.

Covin, T.J., Sighetler, K.W., Kolenko, T.A., Tudor, K.R. (1996), "An investigation of post-acquisition satisfaction with the merger", *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 32(2):125-37.

Craven, A. (2004), "People a priority at HP: managing the aftermath of a mega-merger", *Development and Learning in Organizations*, 18 (2):19-21.

Csoka, L. S. (1997), "HR Challenges in Mergers and Acquisitions", *HR Executive Review*, 5(2):1-17.

Department of Census and Statistics. (2005), *Bulletin of labour force statistics of Sri Lanka-August 2005*, Available <http://www.statistics.gov.lk>

Dolan, R., Weil, T.P. (1998), "Mergers: Enhancing Human Resources Management", *Physician Executive*, 24(2).

Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., Davis-LaMastro, V. (1990), "Perceived organizational support and employee diligence, commitment, and innovation", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 75(1):51-9.

Elliot, T.R., Maples, S. (1991), "Stress management training for employees experiencing corporate acquisition", *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 28(3):107-14.

Griffith, V. (2000), "The people factor in post – merger integration", *Strategy & Business*, 20 (3): 83-90.

Gugler, K., Yurtoglu, B.B. (2004), "The effects of mergers on company employment in the USA and Europe", *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 22: 481– 502.

Horwitz, F.M., Anderssen, K., Bezudenhout, A., Cohen, S., Kirsten, F., Mosoeunyane, K., Smith, N., Thole, K., van Heerden, A. (2002), "Due diligence neglected: managing human resources and

organisational culture in mergers and acquisitions”, *South African Journal of Business Management*, 33(1): 1-10.

Huang, C.T.W., Kleiner, B.H. (2004), “New developments concerning managing mergers and acquisitions”, *Management Research News*, 27(4/5): 54- 62.

Hunsaker, P.L., Coombs, M.W. (1988), “Mergers and acquisitions: managing the emotional stress”, *Personnel*, Vol. 67 (March): 56-63.

Ivancevich, J.M., Schweiger, D.M., Power, F.R. (1987), “Strategies for managing human resources during mergers and acquisitions”, *Human Resource Planning*, 10 (1): 19-35.

Kerr, C. (1995), “Human resourcing following a merger”, *The International Journal of Career Management*, 17(2): 7-9.

Kusstascher, V. (2006), “Cultivating positive emotions in mergers and acquisitions”, *Advances in Mergers and Acquisitions*, 5: 91-103.

Lengle, R.H., Daft, R.L. (1988), “The selection of communication media as an executive skill”, *Academy of Management Executive*, 2: 225-32

Marks, M.L. (2006), “Workplace recovery after mergers, acquisitions, and downsizings: facilitating individual adaptation to major organizational transitions”, *Organizational Dynamics*, 35(4): 384–399.

Marks, M.L., Mirvis, P.H. (1992), “Tracking impact of mergers”, *Personnel Journal*, 71(4): 70-6.

Marks, M.L., Mirvis, P.H. (1996), “The merger syndrome: when corporate cultures clash”, *Psychology Today*, October: 3-6.

Marks, M.L., Mirvis, P.H. (1997), “Revisiting the merger syndrome: crisis management”, *Mergers & Acquisitions*, 32(1): 35–40.

- Marks, M.L., Mirvis, P.H. (2001), "Making mergers and acquisitions work: strategic and psychological preparation", *Academy of Management Executive*, 15(2): 80-95.
- McEntire, M.H., Bentley, J.C. (1996), "When rivals become partners: acculturation in a newly-merged organization", *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 4(2):154-74.
- Millward, L., Kyriakidou, O. (2004), "Linking pre- and post-merger identities through the concept of career", *Career Development International*, 9 (1): 12-27.
- Mirvis, P.H. (1985), "Negotiations after the sale: the roots and ramifications of conflict in an acquisition", *Journal of Occupational Behaviour*, 6 (1): 65-84.
- Napier, N.K. (1989), "Mergers and acquisitions, human resource issues and outcomes: a review and suggested typology", *Journal of Management Studies*, 26 (3): 271-288.
- Napier, N.K., Simmons, G., Stratton, K. (1989), "Communication during a merger: the experience of two banks", *Human Resource Planning*, 12 (2): 105-22.
- Nikandrou, I., Papalexandris, N., Bourantas, D. (2000), "Gaining employee trust after acquisition: implications for managerial action", *Employee Relations*, 22(4): 334-55.
- Papadakis, V.M. (2005), "The role of broader context and the communication program in merger and acquisition implementation success", *Management Decision*, 43(2): 236-255.
- Pikula, D. A. (1999), *Mergers and acquisition: organizational culture and HR issues*. Current issues series, Industrial relations centre, Queen's university, Canada.
- Pollitt, D. (2004), "Alliance Unichem uses 360-degree feedback to improve performance and integrate cultures and values following a merger", *Human resource Management*, 12(1): 27-29.

- Riad, S. (2007), "Of mergers and cultures: "What happened to shared values and joint assumptions?", *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 20(1): 26-43.
- Rhoades, S.A. (1998), "The efficiency effects of bank mergers: an overview of case studies of nine mergers", *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 22 (3): 273-91.
- Richardson, P., Denton, D.K. (1996), "Communicating change", *Human Resource Management*, 35(2): 203-16.
- Risberg, A. (1997), "Ambiguity and communication in cross-cultural acquisitions: towards a conceptual framework", *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 257-66.
- Schneider, S.C., Dunbar, R.L. (1992), "A psychoanalytic reading on hostile takeover events", *Academy of Management*, 17(3): 537-59.
- Schraeder, M., Self, D.R. (2003), "Enhancing the success of mergers and acquisitions: an organizational culture perspective", *Management Decision*, 41(5): 511-522.
- Schuler, R., Jackson, S. (2001), "HR Issues and activities in mergers and acquisitions", *European Management Journal*, 19(3): 239-53.
- Schweiger, D., DeNisi, A. (1991), "The effects of communication with employees following a merger: a longitudinal field experiment", *Academy of Management Journal*, 34 (1): 110-35.
- Schweiger, D.M., Weber, Y. (1989), "Strategies for managing human resources during mergers and acquisitions: an empirical investigation" *Human Resource Planning*, 12(2): 69-86.
- Shirley, R.C. (1973), "Analysis of employee and physician attitudes toward hospital merger", *Academy of Management Journal*, 16 (3): 465-80.

Stahl, G.K., Voigt, A. (2004), "Impact of cultural differences on merger and acquisition performance: a critical research review and an integrative model", *Advances in Mergers and Acquisitions*, 4: 51-82.

Tetenbaum, T.J. (1999), "Beating the odds of merger and acquisition failure: seven key practices that improve the chance for expected integration and synergies", *Organizational Dynamics*, 28(2): 22-36.

Waight, C. L. (2004), "HRD involvement in the investigative phase of a merger and acquisition", *International Journal of Training and Development*, 8(2):157-169.

Yeung, A.K.O., Brockbank, J.W., Ulrich, D.O. (1991), "Organizational culture and human resource practices: an empirical assessment", in Woodman, R., Pasmore, W. (Eds), *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, JAI Press., Greenwich, CT, Vol. 3 pp.161-80.

Tables

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

Characteristic	Total (N=109)		AB (N=57)		CD (N=52)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Age: Bellow 35	61	56	39	68	22	42
35 or above	48	44	18	32	30	58
Gender: Male	54	50	24	42	22	42
Female	55	50	33	58	30	58
Marital status: Unmarried	59	54	28	49	31	60
Married	50	46	29	51	21	40
Profession: Professional banker	27	25	13	23	14	27
Accountant	39	35	15	26	24	46
IT professional/Legal officer	28	26	20	35	8	15
Banking Assistant	15	14	9	16	6	12

Table 2: The level of satisfaction with the information received

Type of information received	Total sample	Bank			
		AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
	t			Sig.(2-tailed)	
Changes in bank's identity	2.32 (.94)	2.92 (.77)	1.65 (.59)	9.59	.000***
Changes in management/administration system	2.46 (.93)	3.14 (.66)	1.73 (.56)	11.89	.000***
About your job security	2.58 (1.05)	3.35 (.76)	1.75 (.58)	12.26	.000***
Changes in reporting relations	2.92 (.73)	3.38 (.55)	2.42 (.53)	9.15	.000***
Changes in career paths	2.94 (1.07)	3.51 (1.15)	2.31 (.46)	7.25	.000***
Changes to bank's policies	2.43 (.51)	2.47 (.53)	2.38 (.49)	.90	.370
Changes in salary & other financial benefits	2.83 (.40)	2.72 (.49)	2.94 (.23)	3.06	.003**
Changes in performance evaluation system	2.64 (.55)	2.77 (.50)	2.50 (.57)	2.61	.010**

Notes: **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 3: The level of satisfaction with the information received by age, gender and marital status

Type of information received	Age				Gender				Marital status			
	Bellow 35 Yrs Mean (SD)	35 Yrs or above Mean (SD)	t-test		Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	t-test		Married Mean (SD)	Unmarried Mean (SD)	t-test	
			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Changes in bank's identity	2.56 (.95)	2.02 (.83)	3.11	.002**	2.22 (.90)	2.42 (.97)	1.08	.279	2.40 (.96)	2.25 (.92)	-.80	.423
Changes in management/ administration systems	2.72 (.93)	2.15 (.85)	3.32	.001***	2.41 (1.00)	2.53 (.87)	.66	.508	2.46 (1.01)	2.47 (.87)	.08	.936
About your job security	2.87 (.99)	2.23 (1.03)	3.27	.001***	2.59 (1.03)	2.58 (1.08)	-.053	.958	2.60 (1.12)	2.58 (1.00)	-.11	.908
Changes in reporting relations	3.08 (.73)	2.73 (.67)	2.57	.011**	2.76 (.75)	3.09 (.67)	2.42	.017**	2.98 (.79)	2.88 (.67)	-.70	.484
Changes in career paths	2.95 (1.01)	2.92 (.91)	.16	.870	2.83 (1.04)	3.04 (1.10)	.98	.326	3.04 (1.04)	2.85 (1.09)	-.93	.353
Changes to bank's policies	2.43 (.53)	2.44 (.50)	-.113	.910	2.50 (.50)	2.36 (.52)	-.386	.169	2.42 (.49)	2.44 (.53)	.208	.836
Changes in salary & other financial benefits	2.75 (.47)	2.92 (.27)	-2.24	.027*	2.80 (.41)	2.85 (.40)	.750	.455	2.76 (.43)	2.88 (.37)	1.55	.124
Changes in performance evaluation system	2.75 (.50)	2.50 (.58)	2.39	.019**	2.61 (.56)	2.67 (.54)	.580	.563	2.64 (.63)	2.64 (.48)	.03	.970

Notes: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 4: Communication consequences

Communication consequences	Total sample	Bank				
		Mean (SD)	AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
					t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Relied on gossips regarding the merger	3.33 (.99)	2.47 (1.00)	4.26 (.44)	-11.305	.000***	
Rumours spread around the workplace regarding the merger	3.94 (.55)	3.64 (.48)	4.26 (.46)	-6.94	.000***	
Felt uncertain about my future because of the merger	3.19 (.78)	2.02 (.76)	4.48 (.54)	-19.18	.000***	

Notes: ***p<0.001.

Table 5: Communication consequences by age, gender and marital status

Communication consequences	Age				Gender				Marital status			
	Bellow 35 Yrs Mean (SD)	35 Yrs or above Mean (SD)	t-test		Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	t-test		Married Mean (SD)	Unmarried Mean (SD)	t-test	
			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Relied on gossips regarding the merger	3.30 (1.08)	3.38 (1.04)	-.34	.732	3.52 (1.10)	3.15 (1.20)	-1.58	.117	3.16 (1.16)	3.47 (1.21)	1.32	.188
Rumours spread around the workplace regarding the merger	3.95 (.66)	3.94 (.38)	.13	.896	4.02 (.59)	3.87 (.51)	-1.36	.175	3.84 (.46)	4.03 (.61)	1.82	.071
Felt uncertain about my future because of the merger	2.90 (1.44)	3.56 (1.20)	-2.49	.014**	3.37 (1.11)	3.02 (1.03)	-1.31	.192	2.96 (1.13)	3.39 (1.04)	1.60	.112

Notes: **p<0.01

Table 6: Expectations following the merger

Expectations	Total sample	Bank				
		Mean (SD)	AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
					t	Sig.(2- tailed)
Job loss due to merger	3.14 (.92)	2.04 (1.01)	4.37 (.81)	-13.10	.000***	
Early retirement	3.00 (1.01)	1.89 (.82)	4.23 (.64)	-16.63	.000***	
Transfer	2.74 (.85)	1.91 (.80)	3.65 (.48)	-13.81	.000***	
Better designation	2.89 (.63)	2.89 (.74)	2.90 (.49)	-.07	.940	
Changes in job responsibilities	2.90 (.92)	2.77 (1.03)	3.06 (.77)	-1.61	.109	
Changes in salary & other financial benefits	3.44 (.49)	3.47 (.50)	3.40 (.49)	.72	.468	
More defined career path	2.93 (.69)	3.15 (.67)	2.69 (.64)	3.67	.000***	
Changes in performance evaluation system	3.38 (.70)	3.10 (.77)	3.69 (.46)	-4.85	.000***	
Improved working conditions	2.83 (.97)	2.18 (.80)	3.56 (.53)	-10.61	.000***	
Changes in corporate policies	2.74 (1.00)	2.23 (1.01)	3.31 (.54)	-6.22	.000***	
Changes in management/administration system	3.34 (.88)	2.91 (.71)	3.81 (.82)	-6.06	.000***	

Notes: ***p<0.001.

Table 7: Actual situation following the merger

Actual situation	Total sample	Bank				
		Mean (SD)	AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
					t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Compete for the same job with colleagues due to job cuts	3.29 (.74)	2.43 (1.08)	4.23 (.92)	-9.24	.000***	
More defined job responsibilities	3.33 (.69)	3.35 (.58)	3.31 (.81)	.32	.747	
Improved reporting line	3.19 (.75)	2.74 (.58)	3.69 (.57)	-8.57	.000***	
Improved salary and other financial benefits	2.79 (.56)	2.84 (.59)	2.73 (.52)	1.03	.304	
More defined career path	2.82 (.64)	3.02 (.69)	2.59 (.49)	3.61	.000***	
Higher prospects for training and development	2.85 (.62)	2.96 (.68)	2.73 (.52)	1.99	.049*	
Improved performance evaluation system	2.57 (.53)	2.61 (.49)	2.52 (.57)	.91	.360	
Improved conditions of work	2.83 (.72)	3.12 (.64)	2.54 (.69)	4.38	.000***	
Improved management/administrative system	2.87 (.66)	3.31 (.46)	2.38 (.49)	10.12	.000***	

Notes: * p<0.05; ***p<0.001.

Table 8: Consequences following the merger

Consequences	Total sample	Bank			
	Mean (SD)	AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
				t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Job satisfaction following the merger	2.93 (.93)	3.61 (.52)	2.17 (.64)	12.78	.000***
Committed to work following the merger	3.00 (.69)	3.37 (.61)	2.60 (.53)	6.96	.000***
Improvements in my individual identity as an employee of the bank following the merger	3.28 (.63)	3.37 (.55)	3.19 (.71)	1.44	.152
Felt as if I was given false promises about the merger	2.36 (.96)	2.61 (1.08)	2.08 (.73)	3.05	.003**
Searching for employment opportunities in other organizations following the merger	3.28 (.74)	2.75 (.54)	3.85 (.45)	-11.35	.000***
I have to concentrate planning my future career following the merger	3.57 (.84)	3.44 (.82)	3.71 (.84)	-1.70	.091*
I have to work much harder to keep my existing position following the merger	3.12 (.82)	2.84 (.90)	3.42 (.60)	-3.97	.000***

Notes: **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 9: Consequences following the merger by age, gender and marital status

Consequences	Age				Gender				Marital status			
	Bellow 35 Yrs Mean (SD)	35 Yrs or above Mean (SD)	t-test		Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	t-test		Married Mean (SD)	Unmarried Mean (SD)	t-test	
			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Job satisfaction following the merger	3.03 (.94)	2.79 (.89)	1.34	.180	2.85 (.97)	3.00 (.88)	.83	.408	3.12 (.84)	2.76 (.97)	-2.02	.045*
Committed to work following the merger	3.21 (.66)	2.73 (.64)	3.83	.000***	3.00 (.67)	3.00 (.72)	.00	1.00	2.92 (.69)	3.06 (.67)	1.10	.270
Improvements in my individual identity as an employee of the bank following the merger	3.36 (.54)	3.19 (.73)	1.41	.162	3.33 (.61)	3.23 (.66)	-.79	.431	3.34 (.65)	3.23 (.62)	-.834	.406
Felt as if I was given false promises about the merger	2.08 (1.05)	2.57 (.76)	2.80	.006**	2.38 (.91)	2.32 (1.01)	-.33	.741	2.30 (1.03)	2.40 (.91)	.573	.568
Searching for employment opportunities in other organizations following the merger	3.18 (.78)	3.39 (.67)	1.51	.134	3.23 (.74)	3.31 (.75)	.54	.584	3.37 (.78)	3.16 (.68)	1.49	.137
I have to concentrate planning my future career following the merger	3.80 (.83)	3.27 (.76)	3.43	.001***	3.42 (.87)	3.72 (.78)	1.90	.059*	3.68 (.91)	3.44 (.73)	1.47	.143
I have to work much harder to keep my existing position following the merger	3.09 (.88)	3.14 (.74)	.303	.762	3.01 (.84)	3.22 (.79)	1.29	.198	3.24 (.83)	2.98 (.79)	1.63	.105

Notes: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 10: The level of satisfaction with the involvement of HR function in the merger

Involvement of HR function	Total sample	Bank			
	Mean (SD)	AB Mean (SD)	CD Mean (SD)	t-test	
				t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Organized seminars/workshops on the merger.	2.58 (1.04)	3.14 (1.07)	1.96 (.55)	7.26	.000***
Provided individual counselling	2.26 (1.06)	2.79 (1.01)	1.69 (.80)	6.21	.000***
Surveyed/interviewed employee attitudes	2.57 (1.00)	3.19 (.78)	1.88 (.73)	8.95	.000***
Provided information on changes to employee related policies due to the merger	2.59 (.84)	2.82 (.96)	2.32 (.58)	3.28	.001***
Introduced integrated HR plan for the merger	2.33 (.73)	2.58 (.65)	2.06 (.72)	3.94	.000***
Helped to clarify my role in the bank through out the merger	2.45 (.63)	2.56 (.60)	2.35 (.64)	-1.72	.087*
Organized staff events such as get together and trips involving employees from both banks that intend to merge	2.83 (1.10)	3.67 (.66)	1.90 (.66)	13.84	.000***
Organized outward bound training involving employees from both banks that intend to merge	2.90 (1.090)	3.75 (.60)	1.98 (.67)	14.49	.000***

Notes: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 11: The level of satisfaction with the involvement of HR function in the merger by age, gender and marital status

Involvement of HR function	Age				Gender				Marital status			
	Bellow 35 Yrs Mean (SD)	35 Yrs or above Mean (SD)	t-test		Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	t-test		Married Mean (SD)	Unmarried Mean (SD)	t-test	
			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Organized seminars/workshops on the merger.	2.93 (.99)	2.13 (.93)	4.31	.000***	2.57 (.98)	2.58 (1.11)	.03	.969	2.56 (1.09)	2.59 (1.01)	.16	.870
Provided individual counselling	2.56 (1.00)	1.90 (1.03)	3.35	.001***	2.28 (.99)	2.25 (1.14)	-.11	.910	2.24 (1.07)	2.29 (1.06)	.23	.816
Surveyed/interviewed employee attitudes	2.85 (.92)	2.21 (.98)	3.49	.001***	2.57 (.98)	2.56 (1.03)	-.05	.957	2.60 (.92)	2.54 (1.07)	-.29	.767
Provided information on changes to employee related policies due to the merger	2.70 (.90)	2.44 (.74)	1.66	.100	2.52 (.92)	2.65 (.75)	.84	.401	2.68 (.91)	2.51 (.77)	-1.06	.291
Introduced integrated HR plan for the merger	2.41 (.69)	2.23 (.77)	1.28	.203	2.30 (.69)	2.36 (.77)	.47	.634	2.36 (.80)	2.31 (.67)	-.38	.699
Helped to clarify my role in the bank through out the merger	2.49 (.62)	2.40 (.64)	.787	.433	2.46 (.63)	2.43 (.63)	-.21	.827	2.48 (.64)	2.42 (.62)	-.46	.645
Organized staff events such as get together and trips involving employees from both banks that intend to merge	2.93 (1.02)	2.69 (.90)	1.20	.231	2.67 (1.08)	2.98 (1.11)	1.49	.137	3.06 (.95)	2.63 (1.12)	-2.10	.037*
Organized outward bound training involving employees from both banks that intend to merge	3.00 (1.12)	2.79 (.87)	1.02	.306	2.80 (1.12)	3.01 (1.06)	1.06	.292	3.16 (.93)	2.69 (1.17)	-2.29	.024*

Notes: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.